

Probabilistic Sensitivity Studies of Composite Damage Models

ICCM 23

International Conference on Composite Materials

Belfast

30 July – 4 August 2023

David Riha, Matthew Kirby, and Marcus Stanfield

Southwest Research Institute

Distribution A. Approved for Public
Release: Unlimited Distribution (AFRL-
2023-2442 Cleared: 5/18/2023)

- I. Background: Process-to-Performance Composites Modeling Framework
- II. Model Verification and Validation (V&V) and Uncertainty Quantification (UQ)
- III. Open-Hole Tension Study Objectives and Model Development
- IV. Probabilistic Analysis Approach
 1. Random Variables
 2. Response Surface Modeling
- V. Probabilistic Analysis Results and Discussion
- VI. Summary and Conclusions

- ▶ **Bonded composite primary structures for advanced aircraft systems**
 - ▶ **Advantages:** (1) reduced weight, (2) reduced part count, and (3) improved performance
 - ▶ **Challenges:** (1) limited software tools for design and analysis, (2) impact of uncertainties and manufacturing defects not well understood², and (3) fasteners used because bond is not trusted

- ▶ **OPPERA Program: OMC (Organic Matrix Composite) Process-to-Performance Evaluation, Research, and Analysis**
 - ▶ **Program objective:** Develop validated process-to-performance (P2P) methods to predict static response and fatigue life of bonded composite structures → reduce cost and schedule impacts during certification
 - ▶ **Demonstration article:** bonded composite pi-preform joint
 - ▶ **Study objective:** develop engineering tool for assessing structural response of bonded composite pi-joints under uncertainty

- ▶ **Research question:** Identify opportunities to mature probabilistic approaches in the P2P framework

Pi-joint Demonstration Article¹

[1] Flansburg et al., AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials Conference, 2009.

[2] Omairey et al., SN Applied Sciences, 2021.

▶ **Multiscale framework for process-to-performance (P2P) modeling** → mesoscale fiber architecture to macroscale component response

▶ **Flexible** → multiple paths through the framework to capture various phenomena and allow for flexibility in solution fidelity

▶ **Predictive Capability**

1. Fiber bed compaction and relaxation
2. Material properties, residual stresses, and porosity evolution during cure
3. Damage evolution at mesoscale and macroscale
4. Final part capability

- ▶ Systematic approach for identifying important phenomena, approximations, and uncertainties
- ▶ Guides resource allocation for gathering experimental data to reduce uncertainty (e.g. sensitivity analysis)
- ▶ Formal documentation of assumptions, limitations, and justification of results with supporting data
- ▶ Some key elements of V&V approach:
 - ▶ Phenomena importance and ranking table (PIRT): used to understand key phenomena and capabilities for modeling the phenomena
 - ▶ Tool maturity level (TML): formal assessment of the predictive capability of the model

▶ **NESSUS® 10.0 probabilistic analysis software**

- ▶ Model inputs can be defined as random variables and described by a probability density function
- ▶ Probabilistic methods are used to propagate uncertainties through models and compute variance-based sensitivities
- ▶ Estimate the contribution from aleatory (inherent variations) and epistemic (knowledge-based) uncertainty

▶ **Sensitivities are dependent on...**

- ▶ Strength of the correlation between the input parameter and the response
- ▶ Range of variation for the random variable in the analysis

- ▶ Supports identifying steps that could be taken to reduce uncertainty in model predictions and mature models/framework

- ▶ Investigate the relationship between uncertainty in mechanical and fracture properties and variability in the maximum load for different layup configurations
- ▶ Identify potential opportunities for reducing uncertainty in the model prediction
- ▶ Guide resource allocation for further data collection
- ▶ Mature probabilistic modeling in the P2P framework

▶ Geometry:

- ▶ ASTM D5766 → L = 6", W = 1.5", and $\varnothing = 0.25"$
- ▶ Minimum element size near the hole = 1.81 mils (0.046 mm)
- ▶ 8-ply quasi-isotropic layups (7.2 mils thick/ply)
 1. $[45/0/-45/90]_S$ **LaRC04 initiated MIC failure**
 2. $[0/45/90/-45]_S$
 3. $[90/-45/0/45]_S$ **CFV fiber failure**

▶ Material:

- ▶ 8552-1/IM7 unitape ply-level orthotropic properties (homogenized each ply → not explicitly modeling fiber architecture)
- ▶ BSAM material 105 to capture nonlinear shear stress-strain

▶ Damage Modeling:

- ▶ BSAM crack type 101 for matrix cracking
- ▶ Matrix crack initiation according to LaRC04 criterion
- ▶ Interface between plies modeled by Turon-Camanho cohesive zone
- ▶ Critical failure volume (CFV) for fiber failure

- ▶ Maximum load = the maximum load at (or prior to) CFV failure
- ▶ CFV failure is predicted when the average failure load factor (AFLF) goes below 1 for any 0° ply → scaling factor based on current strength vs. applied load

Distribution A. Approved for Public Release: Unlimited Distribution (AFRL-2023-2442 Cleared: 5/18/2023)

Summary of Open-Hole Tension PIRT

OHT BSAM Model Variable	Nominal Value	Units	Sensitivity Study Distribution	Distribution Parameters	Relative Importance of Variation	Confidence
MATERIAL SYSTEM: 8552/IM7 UNIDIRECTIONAL TAPE						
Material Orthotropic Constitutive Model						
Elastic modulus longitudinal tension (E_{11})	162	GPa	Normal	$\mu = 162, \sigma = 3.59$	Medium	High
Elastic modulus transverse tension (E_{22})	8.95	GPa	Normal	$\mu = 8.95, \sigma = 0.293$	Medium	High
Poisson's ratio in-plane (ν_{12})	0.316		Normal	$\mu = 0.3156, \sigma = 0.0167$	Medium	High
Shear stress-strain curve in-plane (τ_{12})	83.4	MPa	Normal (delta vector scaling)	$\mu = 83.4, \sigma = 1.33$	High	High
Strength Properties						
Normal strength longitudinal tension (S_{11})	2559	MPa	Normal	$\mu = 2559, \sigma = 102$	High	High
Normal strength transverse tension (S_{22})	64.0	MPa	Normal	$\mu = 64.0, \sigma = 5.91$	Medium	Low
Shear strength in-plane offset ($S\tau_{12,offset}$)	0.8		Uniform	$a = 0.65, b = 0.95$	Medium	Low

OHT BSAM Model Variable	Nominal Value	Units	Sensitivity Study Distribution	Distribution Parameters	Relative Importance of Variation	Confidence
MATERIAL SYSTEM: 8552/IM7 UNIDIRECTIONAL TAPE						
Cohesive Zone Properties (Bi-linear)						
Mode I interlaminar energy release rate (G_n)	0.331	mm·N/mm ²	Normal	$\mu = 0.331, \sigma = 0.0170$	Medium	Medium
Mode II interlaminar energy release rate (G_s)	0.677	mm·N/mm ²	Normal	$\mu = 0.677, \sigma = 0.0122$	High	Medium
Mode II intralaminar energy release rate ($G_{s,intra}$)	1.28	mm·N/mm ²	Normal (CV = 5.14%)	$\mu = 1.28, \sigma = 0.0657$	High	Low
Mixed mode exponent, Mode I and Mode II interlaminar (η)	2.2		Shifted Lognormal (-1)	$\mu = 1.104, \sigma = 0.3815 (\lambda = 0.0425, \zeta = 0.3359)$	High	Medium
Critical Failure Volume (CFV)						
Weibull modulus, shape parameter (α)	41.0		Lognormal	$\mu = 41.3342, \sigma = 5.5622 (\lambda = 3.7127, \zeta = 0.1340)$	High	Medium

Distribution A. Approved for Public Release: Unlimited Distribution (AFRL-2023-2442 Cleared: 5/18/2023)

- ▶ Ranked variables based on team’s experience with quasi-isotropic OHT coupon testing
 - ▶ Relative importance of uncertainty and variation in the parameter
 - ▶ Confidence in the models and data
- ▶ 12 random variables in the probabilistic studies:

Distribution A. Approved for Public Release: Unlimited Distribution (AFRL-2023-2442 Cleared: 5/18/2023)

Generate Training Data (≥ 26 samples)

Sensitivity Study using RSM (10,000 samples)

NESSUS Response Surface Toolkit

Epistemic Sensitivity Factors

Maximum Load (Epistemic)

Distribution A. Approved for Public Release: Unlimited Distribution (AFRL-2023-2442 Cleared: 5/18/2023)

Aleatory Sensitivity Factors

- Differences between layups strongly influenced by position of 0° plies
- Layup 2** is more sensitive to shear than other layups because 0° plies are on boundary (less constraint on matrix cracking)
- Layups 1 and 3:**
 - 0° plies positioned between two 45° plies → limit shear cracking initiation and propagation
 - Exhibit similar sensitivity results, but...
 - Differ slightly in sensitivity to intralaminar Mode II fracture and the shear strength offset parameter
 - Layup 1 may be more susceptible to matrix cracking (and subsequently delamination) than Layup 3

Maximum Load (Aleatory)

Distribution A. Approved for Public Release: Unlimited Distribution (AFRL-2023-2442 Cleared: 5/18/2023)

OPPERA Max Load Cumulative Distribution Functions

- ▶ Range of the nominal prediction represents the aleatory uncertainty
- ▶ Layup 2 exhibits the most aleatory uncertainty related to uncertainty in $S_{\tau_{12,offset}}$ → investigate in future work
- ▶ Significant difference in max load response between Layup 1 and 3
- ▶ Confidence bounds represent the epistemic uncertainty
- ▶ Substantial epistemic uncertainty primarily caused by uncertainty in α → additional testing could reduce epistemic uncertainty

- ▶ The response of each layup is strongly influenced by position of 0° plies
 - ▶ Layup 2 was more sensitivity to shear → need to characterize shear strength offset
 - ▶ Layups 1 and 3 were primarily sensitive to longitudinal tensile strength
 - ▶ Significant difference between max load response of Layup 1 and 3 requires additional investigation

- ▶ Commonality among all 3 layups = sensitive to epistemic uncertainty in CFV parameter
 - ▶ Collecting more data could reduce uncertainty
 - ▶ However, this parameter is very hard to measure → consider calibrating directly from open-hole tension experiments

- ▶ These types of probabilistic studies can help
 - ▶ Identify opportunities for more efficient calibration of progressive damage models
 - ▶ Support the development of novel tests or stacking sequences to isolate phenomena

- ▶ **Current efforts include:**
 - ▶ **Developing framework for rapid calibration of progressive damage models for new materials to augment certification testing**
 - ▶ **Multi-scale models of OHT/OHC of 3D textiles.**

Backup Slides

- ▶ Results shown at the maximum load
- ▶ Matrix cracks run parallel to ply orientation
- ▶ Delamination pattern is more difficult to discern
- ▶ In general, more matrix damage appears to have occurred prior to the maximum load than interlaminar damage
- ▶ Delamination appears to initiate at free surfaces

Distribution A. Approved for Public Release: Unlimited Distribution (AFRL-2023-2442 Cleared: 5/18/2023)